

In a well-designed road junction, there is no need for a policeman.

By Riccardo Antonini

Abstract

This article is an explicitly a critique of any form of *leadership* that favors for some kind *authority* acquired "forever" and on the basis of "special and rare" characteristics of some "particular" individual and also mentions some benefits of the so-called participatory processes. In fact, it proposes leadership as a **fungible** function and not as a **permanent status**. Moreover, we will try to argue that this function, regardless of whether it is fungible or permanent, is not always necessary for the proper functioning of an organization.

Steps for an etology of the Boss:: *primum inter pares?*

First of all, it can be observed that whoever acts as a *leader* is a *leader* when and only when he actually **acts** as such (and not because he is **declared** as such by anyone or even simply by himself). Moreover, if not just anyone, at least many, within a group, albeit, obviously, at **different** times, could exercise their function of leadership towards the other members.

The focus here is not on the, after all well-known, difference between the characteristics of "*authority*" and "*leadership*" rather on the *impermanence* of the status of *leader* in an individual as a concrete possibility. Therefore it can be considered possible, and desirable, the **migration** of such status from one individual to another over time - even a very short one- and without (too many) formalities.

The adoption of such a vision, only apparently revolutionary (it can be observed on many occasions), could, among other things, help to put an end to the incongruity of a *top management* unmovable even when "it really messed up in a big way" .

If, more or less consciously, we continue to obstinately consider the *authority* as a **permanent** attribute - almost a "divine right" - and not bound temporally and contingently to specific, objective and verifiable, needs (needs that, besides, may vary very rapidly), we will continue to have a distorted view of organizational dynamics.

As a matter of fact, in today's organizations, can "drive", not (only) those who are qualified to "drive", but (also) who **knows how to be the first** to get to the "driver's seat" (and keep away any other). In principle the two skills of knowing *how to get there* and *how to drive* are by no means incompatible with each other, but it is important to stress they simply are independent hence without any real correlation.

But how is it possible then that companies and organizations survive in this apparently paradoxical situation?

First of all, it should be noted that *desire* (to drive) and the *skills* needed to achieve power generally have **no** correlation with the skills needed to manage and or guide an organization.

The short answer then is that engineering and other forms of *non-managerial efficiency* - intended exclusively in a strictly productive / quantitative key – along with the sheer power of *marketing* have allowed to tolerate, compensating for management oddities, ever wider levels of managerial inefficiency and lack of *leadership*. And this without the companies - and the organizations in general - suffered so much that they considered them as **real** problems. Also because, in the absence (real or presumed) of alternative models, *almost* never different organizational paths have been used to highlight these incongruities.

We will try in the following, within the limits of space of the present article, to better argue these affirmations comforting them also with biological and logico-mathematical reasoning, referring to the vast bibliography existing on the subject (which we can not explicitly mention here for editorial needs) of the statements reported here and that we hope to raise a *dialogue* (not a dispute) between experts and non-experts.

Organization without structure. Need and reason for *empowerment*

Do flocks of birds have a head? Certainly not, yet we admire its evolutions in flocks of *thousands* of them as already observed by the latin poet Virgil (“*quam multi in foliis avium se milia condunt*”).

With all our present technology, however, today we are not even remotely able to do the same in the same way. And, as long as we persist in relying on solutions that provide some kind of "control tower", we will never succeed.

Viruses, and many micro-organisms in general, are another example of organization **without structure**. They are organized but in the sense that they act according to *common rules* and in the *common interest*, even if they do not have a *structure* (comparable with the one, for example, of its possible "host").

There is only one Mom.

The general concept of "*divergence*" is fundamental for understanding these dynamics. In fact, only in a (exclusively) *divergent* system, which is, for example, a tree with its branches, one has that the "children" depend *on only one* "parent". (For the roots it is the exact opposite: everything is converging towards a *unicum*, the trunk.)

Yet it is not always the case, for example, in a *network*, *convergence* and *divergence* coexist and multiplicity reigns.

By the way: And if the true "creation of value" in an organization came "from below", precisely by *converging*?

Should not therefore, *by metaphor*, the "*students*" criticize the "*masters*"? (Instead of how much today, on the contrary, it happens, that the teachers "evaluate" the students.)

In the second case there is only a static conservatism (and it is the situation - literally - "classical") while in the former there is the true recipe for innovation. In fact, creative groups work just like that.

A self-fulfilling prophecy: "*A boss is always necessary*".

Given that it makes no sense to wonder how the history of organizations would have gone if there had been more attention to *self-organizing* skills, there are *biological* and *mathematical* arguments that can help explain how a certain "authoritarian drift" can be produced although it is neither necessary nor free of damage. Moreover, such a theoretical analysis can suggest how we can undo it with benefit.

First of all, in a system that "obeys only one voice" there is a considerable - when not total - *loss* of what we could call "*informational biodiversity*".

Among the biological and mathematical concepts, in addition to that already mentioned, of organization without structure, which can help us to understand the genesis of the "authoritarian paradoxes" mentioned above, there is also that of the so-called lateral inhibition. In extremely simplified terms it can be expressed as follows:

"Whoever shouts first inhibits the ability of others to scream louder than him".

Many biological systems and human organizations are **organized** to present this kind of dynamics. Notice how the *organization*, even in this case, does not depend on a *structure*, which is a third party with respect to the whole of the elements, instead it depends exclusively on the set of *relations* between the elements. This dynamic can be modeled and simulated in an extremely precise manner.

The "*Risk of Change*"

Given that "*not to decide is tantamount to deciding not to decide*" and hence the latin imperative "*quieta non movere*" ("*thou shall not move what is resting still*") is not the absolute and infallible recipe for total security, it is however to be acknowledged that there is in many the perception that problems can increase when departing from *routine*: in change, you may think, there is inherent risk.

Moreover, a decision that comes late is equivalent to a non-decision at all and therefore the critical factor of success asks decision-making times to be compatible with the speed of change.

While you are pondering indeed things can get even worse.

Non sequitur A:

"Since it is necessary to decide in (relatively) rapid times [true], a leader is always indispensable [not always true]".

First we may observe that the **qualitative** division of labor makes sense / is right if it is based on the principle of asking others to do what you can not do yourself as good as others can.

Nor on the principle of asking others to do what you do not **like/want/bother** to do.

The **quantitative** division on the other hand has its rationale in asking for help from others in order to be able to do what can not be done by one alone.

Furthermore, in the "divided work" organization, the following two cases must be distinguished:

Common Effort Common Output

Common Effort Separate Output

Surprisingly - at least perhaps for some - it is precisely the organization, or rather, the excess of *organization*, the key to the interpretation of many (pathological) processes that underlie the development of what we can call "organized civilization".

Incidentally, the field must be cleared of the myth that *technology* is **sympiotically** linked to organization in the sense that "*there is no organization without technology*". This myth is accompanied by its "twin" according to which "*today's organization is superior to any kind of previous organization*", and this because - at least so it is believed - today's technology is infinitely superior to that of the ancients.

History instead compels us to face with organizational dynamics that were yes, mediated by the (relatively crude) technology of the time, but their organizations were not so dependent on it as the organizational dynamics of today are. There is therefore no reason to believe that organizations such as those of the great empires of antiquity were less efficient than ours.

In fact, the organization, as mentioned above, is something essentially related to the ability to establish and maintain *relationships* (in this case among individuals) and depends only *indirectly* on technology.

Therefore, as a further step, the field must be cleared of a second fatal myth. That according to which "*without a leader there is no organization*" - which does not mean that in organizations there is *never* room for a "boss" - but *only* that this bond of *necessity*, which most people take for granted, does have no reason to exist. I will also try to show how the intellectual renunciation of this bond of *necessity* can open interesting perspectives.

In summary: Role differentiation? Yes, but between peers and in a non-permanent way.

Dynamics of decisions and consensus in groups - Further groundlessness of the "*boss myth*"

Even in everyday experience the **difficulties** that a *group* decision involves seem to be so much greater than those that would have a single individual if he acted alone, delegated or not, to make **obedience** appear not only as a lesser evil but also very desirable in many practical cases.

The structure of interactions within a group can be of the two fundamental following types with their consequent **complexity**:

one to many (complexity N)

N

N²

many to many (complexity N²) (not N²/2 because is not symmetric neither N²-N because you have to know how to manage yourself too)

Non sequitur B:

"Since the complexity of" many to many "relationships is high [true (albeit not always)] a boss is indispensable"[not always true].

On the one hand it would seem always convenient to manage the interactions in the "*one to many*" model and this for the **apparent** advantage of **linear** complexity compared to the **quadratic** one of the "*many to many*" model (but *only potentially* "*all to all*").

On the other hand, however, the above overlooks the fact that "the one", the boss, must (or "should be", better to say, since nobody can actually do it) manage transactions to and from all (and in real time, in fact, a boss delay affects everyone). Thus presupposing a "channel capacity" almost infinite or in any case much greater than human capacity. (An efficient "secretariat" can only mitigate not solve this problem.).

In the "*many to many*" model, which would be better called "*some to some*" (and only occasionally

it is "***all to all***") things actually go better than it would seem at first sight because in real organizations the interactions are only with a few elements *at a time*. Moreover, since the transactions can pass from one element of the group to the other in a substantially equivalent way, a redundancy of alternative paths is created which make the system much more "robust" than that based on a single "centralizing head".

The technology, for example in the field of telecommunications, has discovered these advantages a long time ago passing from the "*mainframes*" to the structure of "*distributed network*" as we know it today for example on the Internet.

Conclusions

For everyone, even in the world of business, one's own world, often, is **the** world, and the problems that interest him are bound and limited to there, his horizon may not be able to go further.

And it is also in a world of business lived and experienced in this way that the ancient dilemma between obedience and conscience comes to the fore.

From Antigone that solves it in favor of conscience, to Socrates that instead gives to the obedience an absolute value.

To the present day where we now, at least since the Italian Catholic priest Don Lorenzo Milani's time, and with drama no less than that of Socrates, that "*obedience is no longer a virtue*".

The future will be increasingly characterized by the weight that in organizations will have one approach or the other: obedience or conscience, mere execution or creativity and personal expression.

It should not be forgotten that for Erich Fromm "*humanity began with an act of disobedience and risks ending with an act of obedience*".